

SENSOR ADJUSTMENT AND ITS FUNCTIONS

Avezov Olmos Ravshanovich¹

Associate Professor of
olmosavezov85@gmail.com

Shavkatova Shakhnoza Pulot qizi²

shahnozashavkatova20@gmail.com
Student of the Faculty of Pedagogy

¹Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute

²Bukhara State University

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ANNOTATION

This article discusses the adaptation of the senses. The importance of sensory adaptation and the sequence of occurrence of the phenomenon of adaptation are mentioned. An attempt was made to explain these phenomena through examples and experiments.

Key words: sensor, adaptation, receptor, stimulus, reaction, pupil, retina, stimulus

Introduction:

Sensory adaptation is a process that changes the sensitivity of sensory receptors and their response to stimulation. All sense organs experience emotional adaptation. That is, the emotional awareness gradually decreases as a person adapts to the effects he perceives through his sense organs.

The main part

In terms of the sense of vision, sensory adaptation includes dark adaptation and light adaptation. Dark adaptation refers to changes in the sensitivity of receptors in response to a decrease in light intensity. The process of dark adaptation is manifested by three changes in the visual system. First, the pupil dilates (in terms of intensity) immediately after sensing a reduction in light stimuli. Dilation of the pupil is necessary for more light to enter and stimulate the retina. Second, color receptors or cones become increasingly sensitive. After 5 to 10 minutes of low light, the cones reach full dark adaptation. Finally, the third night vision receptors or rods become increasingly sensitive.

In terms of hearing, our ears adapt to loud sounds when they hit the small bones in the inner ear. Loud sound causes the inner ear bone to contract. This contraction causes a reduction or delay in the transmission of sound vibrations to the inner ear. However, this process of auditory adaptation usually does not work very well with sudden or instantaneous loud sounds. Examples of these sounds are gunshots or explosions.

Taste and smell

Low concentrations of several airborne chemicals can be detected by sensitive receptors in the nose. These chemicals, which we quickly identify, include perfumes or air fresheners.

If the stimuli are not extreme, such as a warm bath or a cold lake, people can adapt to hot and cold stimulation within a second. However, stimuli that are too hot or too cold can destroy touch receptors, and this intense stimulation can be interpreted as pain.

Results and discussion

Entering the living room of your neighbors, you smell an unpleasant smell. You wonder how they can resist it, but within minutes you don't notice it anymore. Sensory adaptation is a decrease in our sensitivity to an unchanging stimulus. (To see this phenomenon, raise your wrist an inch: you will feel it - but only for a few moments). After receiving a stimulus, our neurons become less reactive.

Sensory adaptation reduces our sensitivity, but it has an important benefit: it helps us to pay attention to informational changes around us without being distracted by non-permanent information stimuli. Our sensory receptors are primed for novelty and they free our attention for important things. Highly scented people don't notice their scent because, like you and me, they adapt to their scents and notice other olfactory changes.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the presence of sensory adaptation is a very effective comfort for mankind. Thanks to their activity, people are able to reduce the intensity of pain, adapt to uncomfortable environments, and draw attention to the reception of important information and not to this new effect.

References:

- 1.L.S.Arkhangel'skaya Zavist: psychological sources: monograph. - M.: Russian State Publishing House, 2008.
- 2.L.P.Badanina Fundamentals of general psychology: textbook. - M.: Flint: Moscow Psychological and Social Institute, 2009.
- 3.Mayers "Psychology" book p. 263-265
- 4.Z.Ibodullayev "Medical psychology
- 5.F.Khaidarov, N. Khalilova "General psychology" textbook
- 6.P.Ivanov, M. Zufarova "General psychology" textbook
- 7.<http://www.psychologytoday.com>
- 8.<http://www.kobo.com>
- 9.<http://www.britannica.com>
- 10.<http://www.medicalnewstoday>

